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Embarking on a Journey through Pakistan's Carbon Story: A Blue Carbon Assessment of Ecosystem in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

The increasing trend of carbon dioxide emissions is a major contributor to harmful anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, resulting in environmental pollution, global warming, and climate change. These issues are expected to have adverse effects on the environmental sustainability agenda and the well-being of society. In order to preserve coastal and marine habitats, timely adaptation of livestock practices is desirable to mitigate potential losses. This paper examines the causal relationship between marine and terrestrial ecosystems and carbon emissions in Pakistan from 1975 to 2022, employing an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and Granger Causality approach. The long-term relationship reveals that foreign rents, industrialization, marine protected areas, and terrestrial protected areas have a negative and statistically insignificant impact on carbon emissions. This implies that a one-unit increase in foreign resources, industrialization, marine protected areas, and terrestrial protected areas in Pakistan results in a decrease in CO₂ emissions by 0.15, 0.01, and 0.03 units respectively. Furthermore, our findings indicate a positive correlation between urbanization and carbon emissions. The impulse response function demonstrates that forest resources, marine and terrestrial protected areas, industrialization, and urbanization significantly contribute to carbon emissions in Pakistan.

Keywords: Carbon emission, Marine Ecosystem; Terrestrial Ecosystem, ARDL estimator; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

A blue carbon is the word, that explain carbon store in the area where land and water come together and oceanic ecosystem that exist in high level of dissolved salt. Simply the term blue carbon is that carbon store in the region where land meet the sea area and the aquatic environment where animals, plants and the environment interact together. On the other hand, the ocean and coasts provide an incentive way to overcome the effects of greenhouse gases on the atmosphere, this process is materializing by sequestration of the carbon. The carbon sequestration is a natural process by which carbon dioxide is removed from the atmosphere and held in liquid form. The broader perspective of blue carbon is related with the coastal habitat conservation. The coastal habitat conservation is the administrative process that strive for protecting and restoring coastal habitat and prevent the group of animals and plants becoming extinct. When the process of coastal habitat conservation is destroyed, an excessive amount of carbon is released and return back into the atmosphere. The effects of climate change are also increase when the process of coastal habitat conservation is damage. So, we are trying to protecting and restoring the coastal habitat conservation is important to overcome the effects of global climate change.

The mangroves are trees which grows in tidal in the hot places and saltmarshes are coastal wetlands which are flooded and drained by tides. Salt marshes and mangroves absorbs the excessive quantity of greenhouse gas most common carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Salt marshes and mangroves are helpful to reducing the effects of climate change. The export on coastal ecosystem in Pakistan are poorly resolved (Santos, 2021). The mangroves forest is located in productive wetlands that occur in coastal intertidal zones. The all mangroves are preserved through financing seeking to purchase greenhouse gas emission reductions in the OECD countries. The financing mechanism is cost effective and also financially sustainable (Zeng 2021). The blue carbon ecosystem such as mangroves, tidal, saltmarshes and sea grasses are observing the large quantity of greenhouse gasses from the atmosphere. Blue carbon is a dynamic field but still are not fully mature. The controversies among peoples are the major consequence of lack of maturity. On the other hand, climate change is a risk due to the lack of blue carbon sequestration (Macreadie 2019). The field of blue carbon are vulnerable so that the blue carbon sequestration is very helpful to mitigate global climate change. We need to improve and restore the blue carbon sequestration. The climate change is affecting the environment and humans' health through extreme weather events. Climate change is induced the expansion of mangroves into tidal marshes could significantly increase the blue carbon storage (Zeng 2021).

Carbon reserve in a coastal and marine ecosystem that contributes to the value of carbon that stored in mangrove, tidal marsh and seagrass ecosystems. The vegetated coastal habitats are provided numerous benefits for environment and these coastal habitats are essential for climate change. The relationship between living organism including human and physical environment, tidal marshes, seagrass ecosystem are economically important. Most of the countries are contribute differently to value of carbon that stored in costal and marine ecosystem because the rate of coastal blue carbon sequestration and their shadow price (Christan 2021). The carbon captured by world ocean and coastal ecosystem and the amount of carbon found in organic compound that stored over a long period of time by mangroves, seagrasses and salt marshes can protect coastal region from storm surges and sea level rise. The mangroves, seagrass and salt marshes are acquiring state of being noticeable is a key natural climate solution. On the other hand, a group of trees and shrubs that live in the area where the ocean meets the land between high and low tides considered the most robustly studied blue carbon ecosystem (Yiwen 2021). The reducing emission of heat trapping atmosphere greenhouse gases tp prevent from global warming to more extreme temperature is more important effective at national level especially in those countries that rapidly losing their trees which grows in tropical areas. on the other hand, mangrove is more powerful carbon sink rather than other coastal wetland, they inhale carbon dioxide from the air and store their roots and branches. The shrubs that grows in tidal wetland can sequester four time more carbon then other rainforests, so that these sequestration process can contribute to mitigating carbon dioxide emission if deforestation remain low. While store and sequester large amount of carbon from mangroves, it is possible if falling deforestation rate (Daniel 2020). A fuel formed in the earth from plants and animals remains that using up the resource should be restore to a former capacity in different regions of the country. In the northern regions most of the people are cuts their forest plants for use of heating and for cooking needs, the process of deforestation is increase day by day that harmful for humans and animals. On the other hand, producing and burning fossil fuels creates the air pollution that harmful for human's health and generates toxic emission that enhance the problem of climate change. The country has needed the conscious exertion of power to achieve the food security (Snovia 2020).

1.1. Coastal Ecosystem

The coastal ecosystem occurs where the land and water come together. The coastal ecosystem provides a various set of habitats like mangroves, coral reefs, seagrass beds, estuaries and lagoons etc. The coastal ecosystem is full of plants like trees, shrubs, herbs, grasses, mosses and these plants are mange the whole earth temperature. As these plants grows in coastal ecosystem, pull out the carbon dioxide in to the air and store the carbon dioxide in the tissue, roots and soil beneath. Keep carbon dioxide out of our atmosphere, carbon dioxide is the primary greenhouse gas that trap heat from the sun. The climate change and human effect the coastal conservation, the coastal conservation is an important part of the ecosystem natural conservation. The natural conservation is to protect the natural resources including animals and plants as well as habitat for the future. We need to reduce more likely to buffer the effects of climate change on local conservation. We are trying to invest more in local conservation to the global greenhouse gas emission reduction (He 2019).The country is focused to implement the climate change mitigation scheme to reduce climate change problems. The main focus of these mitigation program is to conservation and restoration of saltmarshes, seagrass and mangroves ecosystem. The Australian country are constituted a mechanism to mitigate the greenhouse gas emission, on the other hand improve the ecosystem services (Serrano, 2019). Coastal discharges include that urban stormwater drains and outfalls for sewage and industry, submarine inflow of fresh water and the water under the surface which is more saline than freshwater but less saline than seawaterfrom land into the sea. The terrestrial discharge is an important component which has been ignore in most of the analysis. So that the new sustainable development goals are under consideration in water budget analysis (Luijendijk, 2020).Natural infrastructure is a system that is either naturalized and then intentionally managed to provide multiple benefits for the environment and human well-being. The natural infrastructure projects like wetland restoration than the other critical infrastructure for funding are comes from different sources. It is not important which infrastructure is important, the important is work together to increase the resilience of coastal ecosystem (Sutton-Grier, 2019).

The tree which grows in tidal and tropical coastal areas having numerous tangled roots that's provide natural infrastructure and protection to the polluted areas near coastline. So that this type of trees known as mangroves are important they absorbing the storm surge contribute extreme weather events such as hurricanes. The restoration and conservation of lost mangroves are essential for deceasing the effects of global warming. The process of replanting and rebuilding the soil of disturbed land might be required for the survival of mangroves. On the other hand, loss of land along the line with a large body of water meets the land due to natural removal of beach in response to change water level conditions. The coastal erosion protects the coastal communities from natural hazards such as tropical cyclones and storms (Shamsa 2019). The high value of heavy metals in large algae growing in the sea suggest that marine organism can be use as species whose characteristic show the presence of specific environmental conditions, seaweeds detecting anthropogenic impact on coastal marine communities. In coastal areas seaweeds is providing a food source for grazing species by

releasing organic matter into coastal water and providing nursery grounds for invertebrates and fish. On the other hand, seaweeds are contributing to the livelihood of coastal community, they generate socio economic benefits for thousands of households specially in coastal communities. Seaweeds forming is important because they connect other blue carbon storage in wetlands and mangroves it is major tool for fight to stop the long-term shifts in temperature and weather patterns (Amjad 2019). The heavy metals are creating pollution such as arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, nickel and lead these metals are harmful for human's health. The heavy metals are cause due to the humans' activities like industrial and agriculture activities. The metal manganese is a most common metal that found in water, air and soil. So that low concentration is a good for maintaining good health while high concentration are dangerous, acute and chronic illnesses are caused by heavy metal concentration in drinking water. On the other hand, the matter that settles to the bottom of stream beds that destroy the natural food chain that's way fish population is decrease. The minute portion of matter is a source of pollution and possess a risk to human's health (Allauddin 2020). The value of an attribute of heavy metals change at different time and different location, naturally heavy metals occurs in environment and important for survival but if they accumulate in organism they become hazardous. The origin of matter that settles to the bottom of a liquid that have potential to reveal the study of chemical composition of earth and its rocks and minerals in aquatic environment. Hence grasps is relating to the events the actions of being made impure by polluting. The evidence of competence courage in adversity to expand progressive conservative plans of action design to achieve for boosting the ecosystem and human's health (Asmat 2021).

1.2. Marine Ecosystem

Marine ecosystem is defined by the two types of essential factors that is biotic and abiotic. The biotic factors are relating the living organism present in ecosystem and abiotic factors refers to all non-living organism present in the ecosystem. The marine water is something different from freshwater ecosystem, in freshwater have a very low salt. On the other hand, the marine water is around the two-third of the uppermost layer of earth. These geographic areas are considered ecosystem in which plant, animal and other organism work together from a bubble of life. The health of the ecosystem is essential for the safety of people and coastal region. The nutrition, health and employment status of the peoples is essential, it is necessary that to give attention on this status. The role of nutrition, health and employment status is an important sector of maritime economy. The word maritime define is relating to the sea with ties to navigation and commerce. The maritime economy is explained that it covers all marketable activities linked to the sea, like fisheries. The maritime economy is an important sector of the economy and play the essential role in economic development (Selig, 2019). The overall decrease in the mass of all species in the community risky for humans' health. The decline of community biomass is the cause of increasing the natural mortality. On the other hand, the higher temperature is the cause of despite faster somatic growth and decrease in phytoplankton. The warming ocean is hazardous, it contributing to sea level rise and melting glaciers. In this scenario highlight the importance of the competition among faster growth and mortality in a warming ocean (Carozza 2018). The mechanisms are controlling the aquatic environment that have a high salt content are capable of being predicted, and how they have been used in forecasts to date. These mechanisms take in physical atmosphere and oceanic process.

The physical atmosphere is one of the most important components of the earth physical system. On the other hand, the oceanic process are Recurrent natural changes that are physical, biological, or chemical, actively affecting the seas and oceans (Jacox, 2020). The biogeochemical are the elements move cyclically from the environment to living organisms and back to the environment and the tendency of an organism or body to maintain internal stability are demonstrated. The aquatic organism, the trophic factor and the organism of biotopes are the adaptation of characteristics, and adaptation is the physical characteristic of an organism that helps an organism to survive better in the surrounding environment (Egorov, 2021). The waste water such as faeces water from homes and factories, which flows away through sewers. The synthetic fabric that release from textile consisting of ultra-fine fibers. The very small parts of matter released from paints and tires as major sources of micro plastic pollution. Ponds, lakes, streams, rivers and wetland are main types of fresh water biomass, the freshwater is state of being made impure by polluting. The micro plastic are plastic pieces that measures less than five millimeters across (Tahira 2022). The metallic element mercury is released into the atmosphere are stored in vegetation and soil, the mercury is entered in the environment through landscape. The large boat is grounded on a strip of land covered with sand and small stone at the edge of water during high tide and then manually dismantled during alternate rising and falling of the sea. The dismantled material is cut into smaller segment and stored in yards on store of a body of water covered by gravel. The tide level is increase then water moves towards the land along the edge of sea that is flood current, on the other hand as the tide level decreases the water move away from the land along the edge of a large body of water. The process of machine to come apart into separate pieces is conducted along large body of water meets the land, poisonous waste from the large transporting ships is directly leach into the ocean (Kakar 2021). The ecosystem is based on guidelines and standard unit used to express the degree for a very large expanse of sea and the line along shoreline should be supported by science containing study and interpretation. The monitoring efforts are absolutely necessary when ocean and coastal areas are suffering from coastal population. Similarly, the aquatic environment with high level of dissolved salt are come across great variation produce by coastal population, catching fish then capture the unwanted sea life while fishing for a different species, greenhouse gasses, extended coastal land to gain additional space for living, and increasing population pressure (Nergis 2021). The marine and coastal areas in the world are under increasing pressure, because of human and natural. Humans are affecting the marine ecosystem and coastal ecosystem through overfishing, outright loss of areas used by wild species, ocean pollution and ocean warming. On the other hand, natural stressors are including predator outbreaks, disease and also extreme weather events. The anthropogenic stressors are land use change, clearing a wide area of trees, and urbanization (Alexander 2019).

1.3. Blue carbon and ecosystem

The word blue carbon having different parts which is immense advantage able and facilitated the being made the part of blue carbon. The communication among a wide range of contributors for the benefit of the act of trying to protect water areas where the depth of water is less than six meters at low tides and its coastal flooded and wet areas. The benefits of coastal wetland known as nature's kidneys that's

very important for the habitat of commercial and recreational fisheries. On the other hand, coastal wetland provides clean drinking water and recreational opportunities. Blue carbon science has a very broad scope that's play important role in climate change mitigation and adaptation. The blue carbon science has now reached the international prominence (Lovelock 2019). Blue carbon ecosystem is some of the most threatened ecosystems on earth. The climate change, global warming and environmental risk are the greatest threat to the coastal ecosystem and marine ecosystem. Here the essential action is needed to prevent further degradation, and reduce greenhouse gas emission that effect the ecosystem badly. On the other hand, it is necessary to reestablishing the degraded habitat (Serrano2019). The coastal ecosystem are the mangroves, tidal marshes and seagrass mitigating the climate change through the process of capturing and storing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and a very large expense of sea. Whereas helping offset the anthropogenic carbon dioxide emission from the atmosphere is emitted by the human activities. Human activities are affecting the carbon stores by burning fossil fuels, changing land use, and using limestone to make concrete. It is important that we develop a comprehensive strategy of how influence the capacity to store carbon (Bertram 2021). The mangroves forests to be found on the area along the cost and the organism like fish, shrimp, and the crabs that take shelter within mangroves roots. The mangrove ecosystem is decline in some areas due to shrimp farming, and rising sea level. Mangrove ecosystem is affected by the natural and human factors as a result of freeing considerable amount of carbon dioxide. The reestablishing, conserving, and protecting of blue carbon is an essential part to overcome the greenhouse gas emission (Farzanmanesh 2021). Blue carbon has attracted the observation of a diverse group of actors further along the diverse system of interconnection between interacting scientist, including prevention of wasteful use of resources and private sector organization, the group of people with the authority to govern a state, and between governments bodies committed to the preservation of ecosystem in ocean and sea through planned management in order to prevent over the benefiting from the resources of these marine resources. A long-term change in average weather patterns that have come to regional and global climates is the significant variation of average weather conditions becoming for warmer (Peter 2019).

The various inherent features of carbon captured by world ocean and coastal ecosystem has also contributed to confusion and fails to understand the concept blue carbon correctly. The misunderstanding is occurred about blue carbon that to what blue carbon really is. On the other hand, the processes that exchange carbon between various pools within the ocean and envelope of gasses surrounding the earth and marine carbon stock is important but only in the element of blue carbon concept (Lovelock 2019).The process of capturing and storing atmospheric colorless gas produce by burning carbon and organic compound and by respiration in the blue carbon ecosystem contributes to blue carbon wealth. The carbon store in marine and coastal ecosystem is particularly relevant element of blue coastal wealth, countries are contributing to carbon captured by mangroves, tidal marshes and sea grass an abundance of valuable possessions because the they have different rates of coastal blue carbon sequestration and blue carbon stored in vegetation and mangroves. The rate of blue carbon wealth is different in different countries is an estimated price that is not normally sold in the market (Christine 2021). Carbon stored in near the coastal area and largest of earth aquatic ecosystem are essential for coastal communities. An additional one coastal blue carbon ecosystem is some of the most threatened all over the world, because degradation and conservation of blue carbon ecosystem in over the world in which major part driven by humans. The scanning of the earth by satellite in order to obtain mapping and monitoring their changes, the remote sensing datasets and different techniques is an alternative tool for measured carbon sequestration rate for each ecosystem. The fineness of details that can be distinguished in an image and more details of a smaller grid cell size can improve the accuracy of mangroves, sea grasses and salt marshes classification (Tien 2019).

1.4. Research questions

The research questions of the study are as follows:

- I. Do terrestrial ecosystems help to minimize the risk of climate change?
- II. Do marine ecosystems help to reduce CO₂ emissions?
- III. Does deforestation, industrialization, and urbanization cause CO₂ emissions?

1.5. Research Objectives

The specific objectives of the study were:

- I. To examine the role of the terrestrial ecosystem in mitigating carbon emissions.
- II. To investigate the impact of marine protected areas on improving the environmental quality.
- III. To analyze the impact of deforestation, massive industrialization and rural-urban migration on environmental quality.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Karani&Failler (2020) showed that the contribution of how Africa's huge marine ecosystem. The aquatic environment in which high level of dissolved salt is an essential component of the global life support system. The sectoral approach is complemented by using secondary data through thirteen African countries from the period of time (August 2019 to October 2019). Blue carbon and ecosystem services are helpful to mitigate the climate change. Their results indicate that the development of coastal and maritime tourism support the nation's wealth. Macreadie, Costa, Atwood &Kelleway (2021) explored the abilities that maybe develop for blue carbon ecosystem perform as absorbs more carbon from the atmosphere than it releases. Enhance the opportunities to cover from destruction and restore ecosystem and the analysis based on 2019 to 2020 global annual fossil fuel emissions. Blue carbon ecosystem potentially that producing good result without costing and saleable natural climate solution. Wedding, Moritsch, Verutes&Arkema (2021) analyzed that economic value of the process of capturing and storing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere in California's costal habitat. The result shows that the accessible information is concerning with carbon sequestration in the land along the coast could directly include into the current implemented policy. In California the statutory, regulatory and non-regulatory approach is implemented to reduce the carbon emission. Quevedo and Uchiyama &Kohsaka (2021) analyzed the perceptions of the group of people living together on sustainable tourism and carbon store in

marine and coastal ecosystems. Whereas the results comparing household survey on the carbon in coastal ecosystem through mangroves, tidal marshes and seagrasses between rural and urban areas of Philippines. The results indicate that a wide difference exist between urban and rural perceptions. Bryan, Viridin, Vegh& Cleary (2020) showed that the loss of mangroves, tidal and saltmarshes, and seagrasses in the consequence of decreased the supply of natural system that enhance social welfare. In West Africa the process of losing blue carbon is harmful due to increase the significant level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. The results conclude that carbon captured by the oceans and coastal ecosystem that is possible and beneficial within West Africa. Hence to encourage the mangroves conservation. Wahyu, Buchori, Kurniawati, & Brana (2020) investigated the impact of developing industries in coastal areas, and what are the impact of policies related with industrialization along the cost zone which started from 2015 in Indonesia during 2015 to 2019. The results of LULC model that loss of carbon store in coastal and marine ecosystem is more than 20% because of the use of land by human and the surface cover on the ground, whether vegetation, urban infrastructure, water, and bare soil. Moritsch et al. (2021) showed that erosion is the gradual destruction and removal of soil in Australia by river in blue carbon ecosystem is that carbon dioxide emitted when fossil fuel is burned. On the other hand, the large carbon emission is likely to cause threat because of carbon dioxide trapping in the atmosphere and also warming up the earth. The study used spatially explicit model to compare secure carbon dioxide to prevent it from entering the earth's atmosphere and its economic value. The results conclude that preventing the erosion of soil existing in mangroves, tidal and salt marshes, seagrasses that's helpful to mitigate the climate change by reducing carbon emission. Ashok et al. (2019) examined the history of liquid mixture of hydrocarbons which is present in suitable rock strata and can be extracted to produce fuels including petrol in the Arabian Gulf (1870 – 2015). The total petroleum hydrocarbons are calculated burial rates and supporting blue carbon that stock in Arabian Gulf. While conserving mangroves, salt marshes, seagrass meadows, and coral reefs is a good way to reduce carbon dioxide emission. Rabaoui et al. (2020) investigated the historical changes of chemical element present only in minute amount in the matter that settles to the bottom of a liquid of vegetated coastal habitats in the western Arabian Gulf. The study demonstrates that long term relationship exists between trace elements and soil organic carbon burial rates. That's way increase in change the biological communities with a single factor such as human population density along the Gulf coast. Angela et al. (2021) analyzed the aim to describe that people living on the water along fluctuating line where the sea meets the land have any relationship with blue carbon ecosystem. The study uses social ecological approach and mixed method approach with ecological assessment of marine plants found in shallow coastal water of estuaries and spatial analysis in Busuanga. The result shows that carbon in coastal ecosystem mangroves, tidal marshes and sea grass for sustainable provision of ecosystem services to people and environment.

Mariani et al. (2020) concluded that amount of carbon in mangroves, tidal marches, and sea grasses extracted in profitable and unprofitable areas and coupling these estimates to the amount of blue carbon during the 1950 to 2014. Thorhaug et al. (2020) analyzed the system that has the capacity to store carbon in Southeast Asia region. The results showed that a group of shrubs that live in the coastal intertidal zone regionally supported the greater amount of carbon found in organic compound over that of grass like plant that live in the sea with corresponding the number of animals placed in a space compared to the calculated number of animals for the given environment. Jennerjahn (2020) analyzed that a slight difference in movement of carbon between land, ocean, atmosphere and living things, whereas carbon accumulation rate within the small tree that grows in coastal saline can be high. The study used time period from (1992 – 2012). The results showed that the state of being uncertain in carbon storage estimates of individual system requires the special subset of the original dataset that covers within system variability. Gulliver (2020) examined that measure of the capability of a furnace atmosphere to impart carbon into a steel during heat treatment are gain from rehabilitating a degraded coastal ecosystem in the upper coastal intertidal zone between land and open brackish water in south Eastern. The results of the study showed that estimated the potential future distribution of marsh found along rivers and estuaries which floods and drains by the tidal movement of the adjacent ocean, on the other hand the barrier separating areas in a vertical way were removed and tidal exchange was restored. Fries et al. (2020) discussed the impact of general term for the human modification of Earth's terrestrial surface and involving biological and physical disturbances have on the amount of carbon stored in forests in the form of biomass, soil, deadwood and litter. Whereas carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide are main three greenhouse gasses that directly affected by human activities and responsible for climate change in Southeast Asia. The results conclude that mangrove blue carbon is influence the process of change under anthropogenic pressure will improve and enable for conserving the ecosystem where land meets the ocean. Alberto (2022) reviewed that a diagrammatic representation of an area of land and quantify the present blue carbon that store in mangroves, sea grasses and tidal marshes and sequestration in the group of plants which belong to vascular plants such as land plant and they grow under water. They studied four of the five marine demarcation in Spain. The result of the study analyzed that 82 percent carbon captured and stored in the atmospherically environment by marine seed-bearing plants is currently managed within protecting areas covering the area of Europe most valuable and threatened species and habitats. Jay et al (2021) explored overall assessment of unique habitats formed by organisms and plants that can thrive at the borders between ocean and land, these organisms and plant live in salt water and changing tides. The study emphasis on blue carbon ecosystem and their management are observed in Busuanga island, Palawan province in the Philippines. The result of the study examined that lack of institutional capacity that is a driver operates by altering the level of more than one driver is the leading factor hinders the efficiency of the management. Ines et al (2022) evaluated that better understand network interactions that are influence the carbon stored in mangroves, sea grasses and salt marshes and also policies on blue carbon in Indonesia. The policy framework for blue carbon ecosystem is to facilitate and enhance the restoration and conservation of blue carbon ecosystem. The study examine result by using Systems Network Architecture (SNA) model, the integrations of SNA in depth qualitative judgment about the institutional are examine important institutions from a person supplying information by questionnaire and their participation from both viewpoints. (Jinkai 2022) explored that different kinds of living organisms are believed to have developed form earlier forms during the history of the earth in blue carbon management policy is necessary to understand its latent qualities that maybe developed and lead to future usefulness that contribute in climate change. This study considers these issues in China and used ROSTCM6 software for analyzing the result. The

result showed that Chinese economy has made development in carbon that is stored naturally by marine and coastal ecosystem management policies. The Chinese government still faces many challenges including restoration of carbon that stored in mangroves, tidal marshes and sea grasses meadows and logistics behind trading assets and securities regarding type of the market.

Yuan et.al (2022) investigates that four possibilities that is subsidy intensity, price on carbon that stored in coastal and marine ecosystem, and tax rate that directly set on carbon price by defining a tax rate on greenhouse gas emission. The study used evolutionary game model, three basic concepts are discussed through this model like Chinese local government, MR, and the firm that demand blue carbon. The finding of the study is that Chinese local government providing sum of granted by the state and business banking corporation tax is essential for blue carbon ecosystem generates credits based on the tones of carbon captured and stored. Frida et.al (2022) examine the gap in regulations, policies and purpose pathways for coordinated global program focused on mitigating climate change through preserving and restoration of near the coastal area and marine. In Indonesia reviews opportunities and challenges relating to mangrove blue carbon policy. The result of the study shows that the loss of natural processes of living and non-living environment provide between species, ecosystem and landscape provided by mangroves due to clearing trees that grows in tidal marshes, so that these environmental aspects have positive impacts on those types of mangroves tress that provide valuable protection for communities at risk from rising sea level. Ken et.al (2022) suggested that bottom level of hierarchy and the number of parent nodes corresponding to a given a node of the tree water use strategies about shrub that grows in coastal swamps, the country use strategies such as leaf level and tree level is helpful to preserving the mangroves forest. The results analyzed that mangroves forest are one of the most valuable and most productive ecosystems in the world, the country use low consumption of fresh water that will increase the productivity of mangroves tress. Over use of fresh water such as agricultural irrigation, consumption of water in domestic level, and industrial use that may lead to enhance the water scarcity problem. Saima et.al (2022) established the historical record of trace element focusing all one's attentions by systematic inquiry to examine the effect of sedimentary profile of different coastal habitats. The study used ANOVA model to examine the contamination level and dangerous environmental effects of trace elements by using data 1963 to 2018. The results analyzed that contamination level have negative relationship between prevalence of trace elements such as cadmium, cobalt, chromium, copper, nickel and zinc and the hazardous effect of these trace elements were low. The major findings that blue carbon ecosystem not only store and sequester carbon but also minimize the harmful impacts of trace elements on marine ecosystem. Andreas, Rohini, Stephan, Oldrich and Niko (2018) the study analyze verity of model's simulation the cycling of water on earth in Europe. The study based on verity of hydrological simulations to check the global warming have any effect on sea level. The result shows that any change occurs in flow of water that will increase the global warming. The Flow of water in stream during prolonged dry water increase in the Alpine region, and decrease in Mediterranean region. A gradual increase in the overall temperature of earth atmosphere in the region of land around the Mediterranean Sea is higher due to the decrease in annual precipitation rate.

GbedemahTorgbor and Kufogbe (2018) investigate the knowledge about the situation of increasing temperature on poultry farms and also adopted the new technique and innovative methods to overcome the rising temperature. The rising temperature level is being observed about one degree from 1970s and that's way these rising temperature are badly affecting poultry production due to the quality of being exposed to the possibility of being attacked for the bird to examined the rising level of temperature. The result indicates that, most poultry farmers are well aware the effects of increasing temperature, the information provided through the media. Carleton and Hsiang (2016) estimated that the economic and social burden of current climates tends to have an additional impact are caused by the future resulting from the influence of human being on nature. Due to the higher temperature level are effected the current U.S crop since 1980. The major findings is that the weather conditions prevailing in an area over a long period that influence the historical gradual development of something of the global economy and also guide how we predict the consequences of future climate changes. Ramin &Younes (2020) examined that economic growth of the most polluting nations have any connection exist between greenhouse gas emission and power derived from the utilization of chemical resources. The United States, China and India are the most pollutant countries of the world; mostly these countries are responsible to releasing the higher amount of greenhouse gas emission. The study use wavelet correlation and partial wavelet coherence approaches to find out these connections from the period of time 1971-2013. The finding of the study is that China and India have positive relationship between economic growth of the country and greenhouse gas emission, on the other hand economic growth of United States are positively correlated with greenhouse gas emission. The final conclusion of the study is connection between economic growth and greenhouse gas emission is not clear. Enrico, Marina and Davide (2019) investigate that nexus between economic growth and environmental quality. The study used Kuznets curve to find out the relationship between economic growth and stability of ecosystem. The study used sample of 32 countries from 1992-2012. The empirical results of the study show that as gross domestic product increases the carbon emission is also increases to moving the point where economic growth of the country is maximum, so that the country increase their economic growth the greenhouse gas emission is increases. The increasing level of carbon emission is harmful for humans as well as animal, that's way the country is trying to reduce carbon emission.

Rubayyat & Khorshed (2019) explore the environmental laws have any positive effect on decreasing the level of greenhouse gas emission. To examined the impact of environmental act on greenhouse gas emission of organization for economic cooperation and development nations for the period of time 1999 to 2014. The study used "stochastic impacts by regression on population, affluence and technology" technique to analyze that the effect of environmental ordinance on reducing carbon emission. The empirical result shows that one percent increase in environmental regulations that will reduced the greenhouse gas emission by 0.017 percent. Shehzad, Xiaoxing, Sarfraz and Zulfiqar (2020) the study investigates the impact of effective use of information and communication technology on carbon emission. The utilization of the information and communication technology is negative related with CO₂ emission, within the area of Pakistan from 2001-2019. The results indicate that the information and communication technology in industries and activities of a person that constitute normal existence have positive role has change in global climate pattern. Ahsan and Chandio (2020) this paper examined the change which the consequence of a CO₂ emission and land that are prepare for raising the crops on the provision of raw material of a

gain that is use for food in Pakistan from 1971-2014. This study used the autoregressive distributed lag approach and granger causality test to analyze the long-run relationship between variables. Carbon dioxide emission and area that is use for raising the crops cause each other through the crop used for food. On the other hand, carbon dioxide emission and the land use for raising crops have unidirectional causality. Piero and luca (2019) the study determine unpredictability above than the degree the long run relationship between rainfall and Mediterranean land annually. The recent and a time well come after recent period that gradual change in the Mediterranean region analyses the average temperature of the surface of sea and air temperature overland. The results show that gradual increase in the overall temperature of the Mediterranean land atmosphere as well as precipitation level will decrease and its cause the temperature become hotter as compare to global average. Guang et.al (2022) analyzed the carbon capture and store by marine primary producers such as carbon store in sea grasses, tidal marshes and mangroves and their capacity to store carbon within the plants and sediments below that compare the potential of different marine primary producers to climate change mitigation and emitting carbon and observing carbon are equal in the atmosphere. The finding that the base of aquatic food web including bacteria, phytoplankton and algae to carbon sequestration have been decreasing human activities have impacted the environment enough to constitute a distinct geological change due to decrease in biomass driven by climate change.

Asmat et.al (2022) studied to determine the allocation of metallic elements that have a relatively high density compared to water in sediments as well as fiddler crab. Whereas austrucairanica is a small fiddler crab found mostly in sandy muddy sediments in low to mid intertidal zone from marine and wide part of river at the place where it joined the sea areas of Pakistan. They found that transport gas from the billions of stars together with gas and dust held by gravitational force to their environment and enrichment in this way with metals. Similarly, the state of being made impure by polluting in sediments and small amphibious crab that males of which have one greatly enlarge claw which they wave in terrestrial display from coastal areas of Pakistan. Jensen et al. (2022) examined blue carbon in terms of salt marshes, eelgrass meadows, in particular, brown macroalgae, carbon stock and sequestration rate and managing policies to inspire a connection with Nordic blue carbon roadmap. The Nordic blue carbon roadmap for management is to maximize the potential of carbon stored in the vegetation and soils of mangroves, salt marshes and seagrasses. The results of robust least square is that carbon stored in coastal and marine ecosystem in the vegetation and soils of mangroves, salt marshes and seagrasses is still insufficient in habitat area. The country is needed to use better quantification in habitat area, especially for macroalgae and carbon stocks. The habitats quantification evaluates using the best available science on living organism consisting of similar individual capable of interbreeding that habitat needs. Howard et.al (2023) analyzed that country have insufficient resources to mitigate additional climate benefits because blue carbon pathways are not being flourished. The study suggested the new science for large algae growing in the sea and horizontal marshy land that covered by the rise and fall of tides. In these categories' human are cause to happen increase the beneath surface of liquid. The results of the study are that country inefficient in protecting blue carbon sink. So, the country has maximized their effect in restoring vegetation coastal wetland. While management of macroalgae and soil particles that transported from land to ocean by wind for carbon benefits. Arkema et.al (2023) inspected that investment in shrub which grows in tidal, tropical and coastal swamps having numerous tangled roots that grow above ground are more benefitted and also increase blue carbon. While fisheries, coastal risk reduction co benefits that grows at beginning level than investing larger mangroves. Major findings of the study are that provide scientific information to the efforts and investments to successfully reach by skill to reduce greenhouse gas emission and adaption goals.

In order to guide the study, the following null hypotheses were formulated:

- I. Saving terrestrial ecosystems would minimize the climate change risk and improve environmental quality.
- II. Conservation of marine ecosystem would likely to reduce carbon emissions.
- III. Deforestation, industrialization, and urbanization would likely hurt the environmental sustainability agenda.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The carbon dioxide in atmosphere are increases due to anthropogenic activities such as the burning of oil, natural gas, coal to generate energy, and cutting down the forests. The earths aquatic environment is absorbing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, although the ocean absorbs 30% carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. As earth warm the water in the ocean also warm and spread it across the world. Since, sea grass meadows are absorbing 35 times as much the carbon dioxide in the same area of rain forest. Table 1 shows the list of variables for ready reference.

Table 1: List of variables

Variables	Measurement	Definition	Data Source
Carbon dioxide	Metric tons per capita	A heavy colorless gas that is formed by burning fossil fuels, and by the act of breathing.	WDI (2023)
Terrestrial protected area	(% of total land area)	Terrestrial regions of land that are reserved for the purposes of conserving nature and biodiversity.	WDI (2023)
Marine protected areas	(% of terrestrial water)	MPA is a section of the ocean where a government has placed limits on human activity	WDI (2023)

Variables	Measurement	Definition	Data Source
Forest Resources	(% of GDP)	All the benefits derived from forest land such as soil productivity, water, fisheries.	WDI (2023)
Industrialization	(% of GDP)	Industrialization is the period of social and economic change that transform a human group from producing and maintaining crop and farmland to mass produced and technologically advanced goods and services.	WDI (2023)
Urbanization	(%)	Urbanization the process through which cities grow, and higher and higher percentages of the population comes to live in the city.	WDI (2023)

The study highlights the importance of marine ecosystem, terrestrial ecosystem, foreign resources and urbanization on CO₂ emission in Pakistan from 1975-2022. The defined data of all variables are collected from the world bank (WDI), that is published by world bank that is international statistics on the global development. The study use carbon emission as dependent variable while foreign resources, marine ecosystem, terrestrial ecosystem, urbanization and industrialization.

3.1. Econometric Framework

The study employed ARDL-bounds testing approach for obtaining short-run and long-run relationship between the variables. The augmented dickey fuller test is unit root test for stationery, the unit root test can cause unpredictable results in your time series analysis. The ADF test is use when the relationship given variable and a lagged value of that variable over various time interval. Since, the ADF test is statistically significant test which means that hypothesis testing involves and as a result of test statistics is compared with calculated and tabulated values and reported the p-values. The null-hypothesis of ADF test is $\alpha=1$ and alpha is the coefficient of first lag value on Y. The problem mostly occurs in time series analysis is stationery. So, we check the stationery of the variable before using ARDL model. The mean, variance and covariance are does not change over time, then the variable is non-stationery or unit root. It is necessary that we check the order of integration, moreover the variables are integrated with different order I (1), I (0). The variable appears as different order of integration then use ARDL modeling approach. In time series analysis to check that series is stationery or non-stationery, unit root test was used. The data is stationery if mean, variance and covariance is constant. In the unit root results that describe that null hypothesis is there is unit root while the alternative hypothesis is either stationary. The p-value is less than 5 percent then we reject null hypothesis that is the presence of unit root and accept alternative hypothesis. On the other hand, in ARIMA time series forecasting when determine the series the series is stationery. The stationery time series which means that the series have without trend.

The ARDL bounds testing approach is a cointegration method for testing the presence of long-run relationship between the variables. The study examined the contribution of coastal and marine ecosystem to mitigating the carbon emission, coastal protected area, marine protected area, industrialization on carbon dioxide in Pakistan for employing the ARDL approach. The autoregressive distributed lag model is based on ordinary least square estimation, moreover the model use when data describe mix order of integration. The ARDL model is applicable on both stationary and non-stationary data. The study adopted the econometric model as follows:

$$\Delta \ln \text{CO}_2 = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \Delta \ln(\text{CO}_2)_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \Delta \ln(\text{TES})_{t-1} + \alpha_3 \Delta \ln(\text{MEC})_{t-1} + \alpha_4 \Delta \ln(\text{DEF})_{t-1} + \alpha_5 \Delta \ln(\text{IND})_{t-1} + \alpha_6 \Delta \ln(\text{URB})_{t-1} + \text{ECT} + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

CO₂ = carbon emission

TES = terrestrial protected area

MES = marine protected area

DEF = deforestation

IND = industrialization

URB = urbanization

ϵ = error term

Granger casualty test developed by Granger (1969) has been examine to clarify directions of the relationship between observed variables. The test has null hypothesis which is no causal relationship between variables, and the alternative hypothesis that is causal relationship exist between variables.

$$CO2_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1(TES)_{t-1} + \gamma_2(MEC)_{t-1} + \gamma_3(DEF)_{t-1} + \gamma_4(IND)_{t-1} + \gamma_5(URB)_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \tag{2}$$

$$TES_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1(CO2)_{t-1} + \gamma_2(MEC)_{t-1} + \gamma_3(DEF)_{t-1} + \gamma_4(IND)_{t-1} + \gamma_5(URB)_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \tag{3}$$

$$MEC_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1(CO2)_{t-1} + \gamma_2(TES)_{t-1} + \gamma_3(DEF)_{t-1} + \gamma_4(IND)_{t-1} + \gamma_5(URB)_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \tag{4}$$

$$DEF_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1(TES)_{t-1} + \gamma_2(MEC)_{t-1} + \gamma_3(CO2)_{t-1} + \gamma_4(IND)_{t-1} + \gamma_5(URB)_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \tag{5}$$

$$IND_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1(TES)_{t-1} + \gamma_2(MEC)_{t-1} + \gamma_3(DEF)_{t-1} + \gamma_4(CO2)_{t-1} + \gamma_5(URB)_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \tag{6}$$

$$URB_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1(TES)_{t-1} + \gamma_2(MEC)_{t-1} + \gamma_3(DEF)_{t-1} + \gamma_4(IND)_{t-1} + \gamma_5(CO2)_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \tag{7}$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. In the following table, the mean median and standard deviation are reported. It is important to observe that almost all variable have positive skewness with the exception of industrialization and urbanization. Similarly, foreign rents show the high positive skewness while industrialization have high negative skewness with them. Whereas kurtosis measures peak point of the probability distribution of real valued random variable. The value of all variable shows platykurtic distribution to the normal. In the given analysis mean value of marine protected area is 0.766 and standard deviation value of CO2 emission s 0.131.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	CO2	FRENTS	IND	MPA	TPA	URB
Mean	0.697000	0.209268	20.36306	0.766377	12.31067	32.38660
Median	0.684096	0.189767	20.23665	0.766351	12.31000	32.68400
Maximum	0.956345	1.033106	22.93092	0.766529	12.31459	37.44000
Minimum	0.544419	0.000000	17.54846	0.766351	12.31000	26.34100
Std. Dev	0.131744	0.206869	1.480661	6.35E-05	0.001637	3.225440
Skewness	0.216113	2.137529	-0.174725	2.006957	2.006957	-0.172129
Kurtosis	1.650057	8.804613	2.041779	5.027875	5.027875	1.897408

Source: Author’s estimation.

The study uses ADF unit root test with constant and deterministic trend (see, Table 3). The results of ADF test examined that the all variable was non-stationery at level and they become stationery at first difference with 1 and 5% significance levels respectively. Moreover, our results showed that all the variable are integrated of order I(1) over a period of time 1975-2022.

Table 3: Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Level	1 st Difference	Remarks
CO2	-0.492(0.883)	-6.177(0.000)	I(1)
FRENTS	-2.322(0.169)	-8.179(0.000)	I(1)
IND	-2.652(0.090)	-7.412(0.000)	I(1)
URB	-1.771(0.389)	-63.271(0.000)	I(1)
MPA + TPA	-1.465(10.541)	-6.632(0.000)	I(1)

Source: Author’s estimation.

The study uses ADF unit root test with constant and deterministic trend. The results of ADF test examined that the all variable was non-stationery at level and they become stationery at first difference with 1 and 5% significance levels respectively. Moreover, our results showed that all the variable are integrated of order I(1) over a period of time 1975-2022. The concludes that arrangements of the present examination have variables are stationery at first difference, afterward with a specific end goal to explore the long run and short run relationships with ARDL bound test connected. The data is stationery if mean, variance and covariance is constant. In the unit root results that describe that null hypothesis is there is unit root while the alternative hypothesis is either stationary. The p-value is less than 5 percent then we reject null hypothesis that is the presence of unit root and accept alternative hypothesis. Tab:e 4 shows the VAR lag length criteria.

Table 4: Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	163.1489	NA	5.20e-10	-7.188585	-6.985836	-7.113396
1	308.9118	251.7723	2.16e-12	-12.67781	-11.46131*	-12.22667
2	352.8350	65.88488	9.59e-13	-13.53796	-11.30772	-12.71088
3	401.5455	61.99515	3.68e-13	-14.61570	-11.37172	-13.41268
4	439.6311	39.81673*	2.60e-13*	-15.21050*	-10.95278	-13.63153*

Source: Author's estimation.

The Akaike information criterion is statistical method for computing how well a model fits the data it was generated from. The AIC are also estimated the number of independent variables used to build the model. The lower value of AIC means that the model is better fitted. Table 5 shows the ARDL estimates for ready reference.

Table 5: ARDL Estimates

Short-run Estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(CO2(-1))	0.311219	0.154940	2.008634	0.0551
D(CO2(-2))	0.549604	0.153868	3.571916	0.0014
D(CO2(-3))	0.460635	0.152258	3.025363	0.0055
D(FDEP)	-0.111162	0.068610	-1.620213	0.1173
D(IND)	0.000503	0.003732	0.134851	0.8938
D(IND(-1))	0.002054	0.004017	0.511335	0.6134
D(IND(-2))	0.002387	0.004302	0.554807	0.5838
D(IND(-3))	0.004525	0.003467	1.305279	0.2032
D(MPA +TPA)	7.623205	5.343450	1.426645	0.1656
D(MPA(-1) + TPA(-1))	-8.669608	8.097091	-1.070707	0.2941
D(MPA(-2) + TPA(-2))	-9.242082	6.617323	-1.396650	0.1743
D(URB)	0.001814	0.008851	0.204915	0.8392
D(URB(-1))	-0.707516	0.566922	-1.247995	0.2232
D(URB(-2))	0.600821	0.313989	1.913510	0.0668
CointEq(-1)	-0.728255	0.145471	-5.006201	0.0000
Long-run Estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FRESOURCES	-0.152642	0.084593	-1.804419	0.0828
IND	-0.015860	0.005026	-3.155336	0.0040
MPA+TPA	-0.037006	0.013978	-2.647431	0.0136
URB	0.041786s	0.003405	12.271404	0.0000

Source: Author's estimation.

In Table 5, the deterministic trend in the model was specified based on economic theory and significance of the model. In this scenario foreign rents, industrialization, marine protected area and terrestrial protected area have negative and statistically insignificant impact on carbon emission, meaning that 1-unit increase in foreign resources, industrialization, marine protected area and terrestrial protected area in Pakistan CO2 emission decrease by 0.15, 0.01 and 0.03 units respectively. The negative relationship between industrialization and CO2 emission shows that country has improve the quality of industrial structure that contribute to carbon mitigation. Result of the study are consistent with the results of (Khalid et.al 2022). Their result suggests that industrialization have negative association with carbon emission, meaning that industrialization are decreases the environmental degradation by reducing CO2emission. The negative relationship between industrialization and carbon emission with the results of (Naseer el.at 2021) for the case of Pakistan, which shows that industrialization have negatively affect carbon emission. Moreover, the coefficient of urbanization is positively correlated with carbon emission in Pakistan. The estimated coefficient of urbanization 0.04 ($P < 0.000$) suggested that 1-unit increase in urbanization would expect elevate 0.04 unit of CO2 emission. The result confirms that electricity production from nonrenewable resources are much higher in Pakistan. The country uses nonrenewable resources such as fossil fuel much faster than renewable resources. That's why urbanization positively correlated with carbon emission. Indeed, urbanization are positively and statistically significant relationship with carbon emission, urbanization eventually increases carbon emission that enhance global warming. The results prove that urbanization is the driver of carbon emission in Pakistan (Naseer et.al 2021). Furthermore, increase in

urbanization is expected to produce more carbon emission, urbanization and CO₂ emission are positively correlated. This result show that urbanization increases contamination of the physical and biological components of the atmosphere system in developed countries. the use of nonrenewable energy increases carbon emission in the atmosphere (Muhammad et.al 2021). Whereas marine and terrestrial protected areas are negative and insignificant effect on carbon emission, if 1-unit increase in marine and terrestrial protected areas then CO₂ emission will decrease by 0.03 units. Which means that preserve marine and terrestrial protected area then mitigating carbon emission in Pakistan. The results in line with the study of Xin et.al (2022) analyzed that marine energy transmission related technologies are negatively related with carbon emission. Additionally, technologies use for saving marine are helpful to minimize the effects of CO₂ emission. Similarly, relationship between marine fisheries and carbon dioxide emission was decoupling, preserve the marine fisheries that will reduce the carbon emission this is good for sustainable environment (Huanhuan 2023). Table 6 shows the ARDL Bounds estimates.

Table 6: ARDL Bounds Estimates

Test statistics	Value	K
F-statistic	5.288735	4

Source: Author's estimation.

F statistics determines the overall performance and significance of the model, the results of bound test for cointegration to estimate the value of F-statistics. In the F bound test results shows that the value of F statistics is greater than the lower and upper bound so that we reject null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis. The results of F bound test explain that long run relationship exist between carbon emission and foreign rents, urbanization, industrialization marine ecosystem, terrestrial ecosystem. The Granger Causality test identified the direction of causality between the variables (see, Table 7).

Table 7: Granger Causality for the Dependent Variable - CO₂

Excluded	Chi-square	Df	Prob.
FDEP	0.533977	2	0.7657
IND	1.078174	2	0.5833
MPA+TPA	10.07095	2	0.0065
URB	6.517968	2	0.0384
All	20.71977	8	0.0079

Source: Author's estimation.

Marine and coastal protected areas have inverse relationship with CO₂ emission, which means that marine and coastal protected areas can help to reduce CO₂ emission. Moreover, marine and coastal protected areas have negative and statistically insignificant impact on carbon emission and carbon emission is the coefficient of marine protected area. Table 8 shows Granger causality with respect to URB and its factors.

Table 8: Granger Causality for Independent variable URB

Excluded	Chi-square	DF	Prob.
CO ₂	1.849345	2	0.3967
FRESOURCES	10.68502	2	0.0048
IND	4.796402	2	0.0909
MPA+TPA	20.19647	2	0.0000
All	61.84535	8	0.0000

Source: Author's estimation.

This implies that change in marine and coastal protected areas would lead to effect urbanization. In the given analysis marine and terrestrial protected areas urbanization are decrease Which means that urbanization effect environmental quality in Pakistan. Relationship between marine and terrestrial protected are highly significant. On the other hand, forest resources are negative and significant effect on urbanization. Moreover, urbanization is developed then country moving to highly deforestation rate this will lead to clearing terrestrial protected areas in Pakistan. Similarly, 1 unit increase in industrialization that will lead to urbanization decrease by 4.7 units. The negative association between urbanization and industrialization means country have low production level, and high transportation cost. Producers use traditional techniques of production and low job opportunities in Pakistan. That's why people did not moving to urban areas. Table 9 shows the Granger causality estimates for FRESOURCES.

Table 9: Granger Causality for FRESOURCES

Excluded	Chi-square	DF	Prob.
CO2	0.204260	2	0.9029
IND	2.948245	2	0.2290
MPA+TPA	25.12687	2	0.0000
URB	19.90293	2	0.0000
All	43.52894	8	0.0000

Source: Author's estimation.

The results show that 1 unit increase in marine and coastal protected areas then forest resources decrease by 25 unit. Similarly, marine and coastal protected area are negatively and statistically significantly related with forest resources. On the other hand, urbanization is positively correlated with forest resources which means that urbanization did not moving to forest areas. That's why urbanization is positively and highly significant with forest resources. Table 10 shows the VDA estimates for ready reference.

Table 10: VDA Estimates

Variance Decomposition of CO2						
Period	S.E.	CO2	FRENTS	IND	MPA+TPA	URB
1	0.025324	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.101157	6.568554	37.11933	0.457670	4.184961	51.66948
3	3.422181	2.756259	40.81611	0.510625	0.826858	55.09015
4	117.6403	2.865590	40.87358	0.507021	0.766080	54.98773
5	4040.549	2.867425	40.87615	0.506804	0.764981	54.98464
6	138776.5	2.867458	40.87620	0.506799	0.764963	54.98458
7	4766406.	2.867459	40.87621	0.506799	0.764962	54.98457
8	1.64E+08	2.867459	40.87621	0.506799	0.764962	54.98457
9	5.62E+09	2.867459	40.87621	0.506799	0.764962	54.98457
10	1.93E+11	2.867459	40.87621	0.506799	0.764962	54.98457

Source: Author's estimation.

In variance decomposition analysis between carbon emission, marine and coastal protected areas, forest resources, industrialization and urbanization over a 10-period horizon are presented. The result shows that variation in CO2 emission is being explained by its own shocks and significantly explained by other variables in the study. VDA analysis displays that 40.8, 0.50, 0.76, 54.98 and 2.86% of future 10 periods horizon fluctuations in CO2 emission due to shocks in forest resources, marine and terrestrial protected areas, industrialization and urbanization respectively.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Pakistan has become the fifth most populous country in the world. It is also experiencing constant population growth, which inevitably leads to increased demand for agricultural goods and livestock production. Meeting this heightened demand for food, amidst scarce resources, necessitates a concentrated focus on agricultural practices. Unfortunately, such practices often result in the excessive utilization of natural resources. Moreover, a higher consumption pattern in Pakistan necessitates a larger reserve of livestock. Furthermore, this study examines the long-term and short-term effects of carbon emissions. These effects disproportionately impact developed countries compared to developing ones. Developed nations, due to their higher energy consumption, tend to pollute more, whereas energy consumption is lower in developing nations. However, the latter often lack sufficient resources to mitigate the effects of rising temperatures. The primary objective of this research is to investigate the effects of marine and terrestrial protected areas on carbon dioxide emissions. Notably, the findings indicate a negative correlation between marine and terrestrial protected areas and carbon emissions. Thus, preserving marine and coastal habitats could mitigate carbon emissions in Pakistan. Additionally, the coefficient of urbanization is positively correlated with carbon emissions in Pakistan. This finding underscores the country's heavy reliance on nonrenewable resources for electricity production, particularly fossil fuels, leading to a positive correlation with urbanization. However, the establishment of marine and coastal protected areas could counteract urbanization. The relationship between marine and terrestrial protected areas and urbanization is negative, indicating that urbanization negatively impacts environmental quality in Pakistan. Moreover, forest resources have a negative and significant effect on urbanization. However, as urbanization progresses, there is a higher rate of deforestation, ultimately affecting terrestrial protected areas. Conversely, urbanization is positively correlated with forest resources, indicating that urbanization does not encroach upon forest areas.

In light of these findings, several policy recommendations are proposed for environmentalists to formulate sustainable long-term green policies:

- I. A shift towards innovative methods for fisheries and seafood production in Pakistan.
- II. Strict implementation of environmental laws to curb carbon emissions.
- III. Implementation of regulations to reduce the cost of green technology.
- IV. Enactment of laws to mitigate the effects of CO₂ emissions.
- V. Introduction of new policies to address environmental degradation, which hampers economic growth.
- VI. Implementation of carbon tax to decrease greenhouse gas emissions.
- VII. Evaluation of the impact of chemicals used in the agriculture industry on environmental sustainability, alongside the introduction of green taxes.
- VIII. Promotion of renewable energy resources through the provision of low-interest loans and the utilization of renewable energy generators.
- IX. Creation of awareness programs about carbon neutralization in the economy.
- X. Promotion of technologies for both non-industrial and industrial purposes to combat environmental pollution.

In conclusion, the government of Pakistan must take proactive measures to mitigate carbon emissions and promote sustainable environmental practices.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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